

Data-driven Lyapunov-based synthesis of feedback controllers for nonlinear systems

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Abstract

Two optimization problems to design stabilizing controllers for nonlinear systems are proposed based on the well-known Lyapunov stability theory. These are coupled with system identification and nonlinear observer design tools in order to deal with unknown dynamics and unavailability of full-state measurements. Moreover, attempts of introducing desired robustness and performance properties to enforce to the control system are discussed. Numerical simulations are given in order to validate the overall approach.

Keywords— Data-driven controller synthesis, Lyapunov theory, Uncertain systems, System identification, Observer design

1 Introduction

Lyapunov theory [11, 13] is one of the main tools to study the stability of equilibrium points for nonlinear systems. Such a theory provides sufficient conditions to establish the (asymptotic) stability of dynamical systems that requires the search of the so-called Lyapunov function, i.e. a positive definite function whose derivative along the trajectories of the considered dynamical system is negative definite. Many nonlinear control design tools make use of such conditions to define procedures that allows one to choose a control law based on Lyapunov function candidates (e.g., sliding mode control [22, 26] and backstepping [16]).

Given that determining Lyapunov functions is a complex task, recent works have introduced optimization problems to estimate Lyapunov functions for nonlinear systems [1, 20]. Then, [2, 6] shows how to couple these Lyapunov function estimation tools with Reinforcement learning algorithms [24] in order to allow their application to safety-critical systems. In such a way, one is able to determine a stabilizing controller using a two-step procedure consisting of estimation of the Lyapunov function and exploration of the actions' space.

Several approaches proposed an optimization problem where the loss function is defined so that its solution not only provides a Lyapunov function but also a stabilizing controller, e.g. in [5, 27]. However, the former only considers full state-feedback controllers, whereas the latter also enables the design of output-feedback controllers by introducing the estimation of a state observer

function into the loss function, adding complexity to the optimization problem itself. Moreover, in both works, the system dynamics are assumed to be completely known.

In this paper, two different procedures are proposed in order to determine stabilizing controllers together with Lyapunov functions for nonlinear systems. The main difference between these procedures and the current literature is the addition of optimization parameters that allows one to enforce robustness and/or performance properties. Moreover, using system identification algorithms and observer design procedures, this paper proposes an approach to design output-feedback controllers for partially unknown nonlinear systems without additional complexity in the optimization problem.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the Lyapunov-based optimization problems to design stabilizing state-feedback controllers for known nonlinear systems. In particular, Section 2.1 uses a loss function that aims at finding any control law that makes a chosen Lyapunov function candidate satisfy the stability conditions. On the other hand, Section 2.2 defines a different optimization problem, where the control law is optimized to obtain a target Lyapunov function rather than any function satisfying the stability conditions. This approach can be seen as a data-driven approach based on the well-known feedback linearization [11] technique. Both these approaches allow the user to enforce desired robustness and performances. However, note that only numerical proofs of these properties are given as formal proofs are difficult to be formulated and verified. Section 3 explains how to deal with non-fully-measurable state vectors and unknown dynamics by reviewing a system identification technique based on Universal Differential Equations [19] (Section 3.1) and standard output-feedback control approaches using high-gain observers [7, 25] (Section 3.2). Finally, Section 4 provides a numerical validation of the various proposed approaches.

2 Full state feedback control of known nonlinear systems

This section focuses on the numerical Lyapunov-based approaches proposed to design stabilizing controllers. For simplicity, it is preliminary assumed that the dynamics of the dynamical systems are known and that its state vector is available for measurements. Then, Section 3 will provide strategies to deal with unknown dynamics and partially measurable state vectors.

2.1 Lyapunov-based loss function

Consider a controlled nonlinear system

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u), \quad x(0) = x_0 \tag{1}$$

where $x \in D_x \subset \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, $u \in D_u \subset \mathbb{R}^{n_u}$ is the input vector, $f : D_x \times D_u \mapsto \mathbb{R}^n$ is locally Lipschitz in (x, u) , D_x is a domain that contains

$x = 0$ and D_u is a domain that contains $u = 0$. Moreover, suppose that $x = 0$ is an equilibrium point of system (1) for $u = 0$ and that u is a state-feedback input, i.e. $u = u(x)$. Using classical Lyapunov stability theory [13], the following proposition holds.

Proposition 1. *Consider the controlled nonlinear system (1). If there exists a continuous function $u = u(x)$ and a continuously differentiable function $V : D_x \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ such that $V(0) = 0$ and both $V(x) > 0$ and $\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} f(x, u) < 0$ in $D_x \setminus 0$, then the equilibrium $x = 0$ is asymptotically stable, $u(x)$ is a stabilizing controller and $V(x)$ is a Lyapunov function.*

Hereinafter, the time derivative of a Lyapunov function V refers to its time derivative along the trajectories of (1), i.e.

$$\dot{V}(x) = \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} \dot{x} = \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} f(x, u). \quad (2)$$

In order to synthesize a stabilizing input function, several approaches make guesses of Lyapunov function candidates V in an attempt to build $u(x)$ such that the hypotheses of Proposition 1 hold (e.g., sliding mode control [22, 26] or backstepping [16]). Suppose that u is a function of both x and a set of tunable parameters $p \in \mathbb{R}^{n_p}$, i.e. $u = u(x; p)$. The purpose of this section is to propose a loss function $\mathcal{L}_1(p)$ such that $p_\star = \arg \min_p \mathcal{L}_1(p)$ determines a stabilizing controller $u_\star = u(x; p_\star)$.

Let a Lyapunov function candidate $V(x)$ be given such that $V(0) = 0$ and $V(x) > 0$ in $D_x \setminus 0$. Moreover, let $B_R = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : \|x\| < R\}$ and let $X = \{x_i \in D_x : x_i \in B_R, i = 1, \dots, N\}$, for some $R > 0$, be the set of training samples, it is possible to define the loss function

$$\mathcal{L}_1(p) = \sum_{i=1}^N (\tanh(\alpha \dot{V}(x_i; p) + 1) + \gamma \|u(x_i; p)\|),$$

where α and γ are tuning parameters.

To better understand \mathcal{L}_1 , take $\alpha \gg 1$ and $\gamma = 0$. Then, noticing that

$$\tanh(\alpha \dot{V}(x_i; p) + 1) \simeq \begin{cases} 0, & \text{for } \dot{V}(x_i; p) < 0, \\ 2, & \text{for } \dot{V}(x_i; p) > 0, \end{cases}$$

one can conclude that if $\dot{V}(x_i; p)$ is negative, then \mathcal{L}_1 is closer to zero, whereas positive values of $\dot{V}(x_i; p)$ add positive contributions to \mathcal{L}_1 . In other words, if for some \bar{p} the loss function \mathcal{L}_1 is close to zero, then one may have found a vector of parameters such that $\dot{V}(x_i; \bar{p})$ is negative for all $x_i \in X$, hence a function $V(x)$ that may satisfy the assumptions of Proposition 1 for $D_x = B_R$. A discussion on possible conditions to ensure that the obtained $V(x)$ actually satisfies Proposition 1 is postponed to Remark 2.

Notice that the minimum of \mathcal{L}_1 is only achieved when $\dot{V}(x_i; p) = -\infty$ for each x_i in X , which is practically unfeasible. By (2), one has that the norm

of $\dot{V}(x_i; p)$ may tend to infinity only if either $\|\partial V/\partial x\|$ or $\|f\|$ tend to infinity. Using the boundedness of each x_i and the continuous differentiability of V , only $\|f\|$ may tend to infinity, that in turn, using the Lipschitz continuity property of f , can only tend to infinity if $\|u(x_i; p)\|$ tends to infinity for some training sample x_i . By choosing $\gamma > 0$, the norm of the control input is also taken into account, so that large input values are discarded and $V(x_i; p) = -\infty$ for each x_i in X is no longer a minimum for \mathcal{L}_1 .

The main difficulty in defining \mathcal{L}_1 is the choice of the Lyapunov function candidate $V(x)$. As a matter of fact, given that Proposition 1 is only a sufficient condition, if one fails to verify the hypotheses of Proposition 1 with some $V(x)$, there may be a different function $\bar{V}(x)$ that satisfies them. In practice, a typical guess for $V(x)$ is a quadratic function $x^\top P x$, with P being some positive definite matrix. As shown in the examples section, this choice will result to be effective in possible practical applications.

Remark 1. *There are several ways to minimize the loss function \mathcal{L}_1 in practice. For instance, one may use stochastic gradient descent algorithms, such as ADAM [15] or the BFGS method [17], and techniques to locally compute the partial derivative of \mathcal{L}_1 with respect to p , such as those explained in [19].*

One of the novelties of this loss function with respect to the ones in [5, 27] is that α can be used to determine the “degree” of robustness of the stabilizing controller. As a matter of fact, the more α is small, the more the minimization of \mathcal{L}_1 will push $\dot{V}(x_i; p)$ towards negative values due to the hyperbolic tangent function appearing into its definition. Furthermore, larger negative values of \dot{V} usually translates into faster convergence rates of the system. However, as previously mentioned, large negative values of \dot{V} are yielded by large input control values, which may not be possible if saturation constraints exist.

The following remark gives a conceptual idea of how to obtain guarantees of the above-mentioned stability/robustness/performance properties. Since those are not easily verifiable, only numerical proofs will be shown in the examples section (see Examples 1 and 2).

Remark 2. *Suppose that by minimizing $\mathcal{L}_1(p)$ with respect to p , one finds some optimal p_\star such that $\dot{V}(x_i; p_\star)$ is negative for all $x_i \in X$. Since \dot{V} is only evaluated over a set of sampled points, this may not imply that $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ is negative definite for all $x \in B_R$.*

In order to establish a condition that guarantees such an implication, one has to make assumptions on the set X and the outcome of the minimization of \mathcal{L}_1 . For simplicity, consider a scalar nonlinear system, i.e. system (1) with $n = 1$. Let X be sorted in ascending order and suppose that $|x_i - x_{i+1}| < \delta$ for every $x_i \in X$. Moreover, suppose that the obtained p_\star is such that $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ is band-limited in the interval $[-2\pi W, 2\pi W]$, for some $W > 0$. By the Shannon sampling theorem [12, 21], if $\delta < 1/(2W)$, then $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ is completely determined by its sampled values in X . Thus, if $\dot{V}(x_i; p_\star) < 0$ for all $x_i \in X$, then $\dot{V}(x; p_\star) < 0$ for all $x \in B_R$.

Using a similar argument, one can use the Petersen-Middleton theorem [18], which is an extension of the Shannon sampling theorem to the case of multivariate functions, to establish that if $n > 1$ in (1), $\dot{V}(x; p_*)$ is a wave-number-limited function and the samples of X are sufficiently closely spaced, then $\dot{V}(x_i; p_*) < 0$ for all $x_i \in X$ implies $\dot{V}(x; p_*) < 0$ for all $x \in B_R$.

2.2 Lyapunov-based loss function with target function

The previous loss function \mathcal{L}_1 attempts at finding any stabilizing controller for controlled nonlinear systems. In this section, a different loss function is proposed that aims at determining a stabilizing controller that makes the chosen Lyapunov function candidate $V(x)$ be close to a desired one.

Let $V_{des}(x)$ be a Lyapunov function for the controlled nonlinear system $\dot{x} = f_{des}(x, 0)$. Furthermore, consider again (1), a control input $u = u(x; p)$ and a given Lyapunov function candidate $V(x)$ such that $V(0) = 0$ and $V(x) > 0$ in $D_x \setminus 0$. Then, define the loss function

$$\mathcal{L}_2(p) = \sum_{i=1}^N |\dot{V}_{des}(x_i) - \dot{V}(x_i; p)|.$$

Notice that a possible stabilizing controller $u_* = u(x; p_*)$ such that $\dot{V}(x_i; p_*) = \dot{V}_{des}(x_i)$ for all $x_i \in X$ implies $\mathcal{L}_2(p_*) = 0$, i.e. it is a minimum. However, even if $\mathcal{L}_2(p_*) = 0$, not necessarily $\dot{V}(x; p_*) = \dot{V}_{des}(x)$ for all $x \in B_R$. Remark 3 discusses how to retrieve conditions so that this implication holds.

Compared to \mathcal{L}_1 , this loss function has the additional difficulty of choosing a desired \dot{V}_{des} that is actually achievable through u with the dynamics (1). A possible way to choose an appropriate V_{des} is to consider the following particular case. Consider a controlled nonlinear system (1) with the dynamics function

$$f(x, u) = \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ \vdots \\ x_{n-1} \\ g(x, u) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where $g : D_x \times D_u \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is locally Lipschitz in (x, u) , and the desired dynamics function

$$f_{des}(x) = A_{des}x = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & \dots & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & 0 & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & 1 & 0 \\ c_1 & c_2 & \dots & \dots & c_{n-1} & c_n \end{bmatrix} x,$$

where c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n are constants such that the polynomial $s^n + c_1 s^{n-1} + c_2 s^{n-2} + \dots + c_{n-1} s + c_n$ is Hurwitz. Let P be such that $A_{des}P + PA_{des}^\top = -Q$ for some

positive definite matrix Q . Then, one can choose $V(x) = V_{des}(x) = x^\top Px$. Using such premises, minimizing \mathcal{L}_2 is equivalent to determine a function u such that

$$g(x, u) = c_1x_1 + c_2x_2 + \dots + c_nx_n. \quad (4)$$

Therefore, the difficulty of using this approach reduces to determine whether there exists a control function u so that the scalar equation (4) is possible.

In several control applications, one is interested in regulating only some of the entries of the state vector x of (1) or a combination of those. In such cases, there exists an extensive literature that studies how to define a change of coordinates to rewrite nonlinear systems (1) into another with the dynamics function (3) (see Section 3.2). Then, determining a function u such that (4) holds, allows to achieve the initial objective. This whole procedure is known as feedback linearization [11] and it is a well-established nonlinear control technique. Therefore, the loss function \mathcal{L}_2 can be interpreted as an approach to numerically feedback-linearize a nonlinear system (see Examples 3 and 4).

Finally, since the target Lyapunov function V_{des} is an optimization parameter, it follows that the user is able to enforce robustness and performances properties to the resulting optimal controller. However, in order to have guarantees of such robustness and performances properties, one should verify the conceptual idea of Remark 3. Given its difficulty, only numerical proofs will be demonstrated in the examples section.

Remark 3. *Suppose that one finds p_\star such that $\mathcal{L}_2(p_\star) = 0$. It was already mentioned that, even though $\dot{V}(x_i; p_\star) = \dot{V}_{des}(x_i)$ for all $x_i \in X$, not necessarily $\dot{V}(x; p_\star) = \dot{V}_{des}(x)$ for all $x \in B_R$.*

Similarly to Remark 2, consider a scalar nonlinear system for simplicity. Moreover, suppose that X is sorted in ascending order and $|x_i - x_{i+1}| < \delta$ for every $x_i \in X$. Assume that $\dot{V}_{des}(x)$ was chosen to be a band-limited function in the interval $[-2\pi W, 2\pi W]$, for some $W > 0$, and that p_\star is such that $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ is band-limited in the same interval. Using the Shannon sampling theorem, if $\delta < 1/(2W)$, then both $\dot{V}_{des}(x)$ and $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ are completely determined by their sampled values in X . This implies that there only exists one band-limited function that passes through the points defined by $\dot{V}_{des}(x_i)$ (or, equivalently, $\dot{V}(x_i; p_\star)$), with $x_i \in X$. Therefore, necessarily, $\dot{V}_{des}(x) = \dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ for all $x \in B_R$.

When $n > 1$, one could use the extension to multivariate functions of the Shannon sampling theorem, i.e. the Petersen-Middleton theorem, to find that if $\dot{V}_{des}(x)$ and $\dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ are both wave-number-limited functions in the same wave-number set and the samples of X are sufficiently closely spaced, then $\dot{V}_{des}(x) = \dot{V}(x; p_\star)$ for all $x \in B_R$.

3 Output feedback control of partially unknown nonlinear systems

This section takes into account possible unknown dynamics in system (1) and the unavailability to measurements of its state x . Thus, using the results of [9, 10], Section 3.1 provides techniques to estimate a model for (1), whereas Section 3.2 explains how to design a nonlinear observer to retrieve the state x and achieve the control objectives.

3.1 Universal differential equations

Consider system (1) with an additional output equation, i.e.

$$\dot{x} = f(x, u), \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (5a)$$

$$y = h(x), \quad (5b)$$

where $y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ and $h : D_x \mapsto \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ is locally Lipschitz in x . Moreover, suppose that the function f is (partially) unknown. Universal differential equations (UDEs) [19] are a class of dynamical systems of the form

$$\dot{\chi} = v(\chi, N(\chi, \theta), u), \quad \chi(0) = \vartheta, \quad (6)$$

where $\chi \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the state vector, N is a neural network, θ is the vector of neural network weights and $\vartheta \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is the estimate of x_0 .

Universal differential equations allows one to include a neural network into a dynamics function v in order to use prior knowledge about system (5) and estimate the remaining parts via the neural network. Letting $\varphi_\chi(t; x_0, \vartheta, \theta)$ be the solution of (6), let

$$\mathcal{L}_3(\vartheta, \theta) = \sum_{i=1}^d \|y(t_i) - h(\varphi_\chi(t_i; \vartheta, \theta))\|, \quad (7)$$

where t_1, \dots, t_d are sampling times.

Finding the minimum of \mathcal{L}_3 corresponds to determine a tuning for the weights vector θ and an estimate for the initial condition ϑ such that they yield an estimate of the dynamics (5), provided that the sampling times are sufficiently closely spaced [9]. Such a minimization can be carried out similarly to the minimization of \mathcal{L}_1 and \mathcal{L}_2 as explained in Remark 1 and the solution of the differential equations (6) can be approximated using standard algorithms (e.g. Runge-Kutta methods [4]).

3.2 High-gain observers for output-feedback stabilization

In this section, it is assumed that $n_y = 1$. The case $n_y > 1$ is not discussed to keep the presentation brief. However, as shown in [14, 25], one can easily extend the following results to multi-output systems.

By [8], if system (5) is m -strongly differentially observable, then the change of coordinates $\xi = O_m(x, u) = \text{col}(L_f^0 h(x), \dots, L_f^{m-1} h(x))$ is such that

$$\dot{\xi}_i = \xi_{i+1}, \quad i = 1, \dots, m-1, \quad (8a)$$

$$\dot{\xi}_m = g(\xi, u, u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(m)}), \quad (8b)$$

$$y = \xi_1, \quad (8c)$$

where $g = L_f^{m-1} h \circ O_m^{-1}(\xi)$ and $L_f^i h(\cdot)$ is the i -th directional derivative of the function h along the vector function f . Furthermore, $O_m(x)$ is known as the observability map of order m and system (8) is in observability canonical form.

Consider the high-gain observer [14]

$$\dot{\hat{\xi}}_i = \hat{\xi}_{i+1} + \varepsilon^{-i} k_i (y - \hat{\xi}_1), \quad i = 1, \dots, m-1, \quad (9a)$$

$$\dot{\hat{\xi}}_m = g(\hat{\xi}, u, u^{(1)}, \dots, u^{(m)}) + \varepsilon^{-m} k_m (y - \hat{\xi}_1), \quad (9b)$$

$$\hat{\xi}(0) = \hat{\xi}_0, \quad (9c)$$

where ε is a small positive constant and k_1, \dots, k_m are coefficients such that the polynomial $s^m + k_1 s^{m-1} + \dots + k_{m-1} s + k_m$ is Hurwitz. It is possible to prove that if ε is sufficiently small, then $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \hat{\xi}(t) = \xi(t)$. However, since f is assumed to be (partially) unknown, then one cannot exactly compute g . Hence, if one uses an estimate of g rather than g itself in (9b), then it can be proven that the estimation error can be made arbitrarily small in an arbitrarily small time with an analogous assumption on ε .

Using the approach of Section 3.1, one can find an estimate of the function g by defining an UDE based on the equations (8) and introducing a neural network into the last equation in order to estimate the unknowns. Note that if f is not exactly known, then one may not be able to determine the correct value for m , thus requiring a guess for its value (typically $m = n$). Once system (5) has been rewritten in observability canonical form, one can design a controller for system (8). A stabilizing controller for such a system implies that one is able to regulate the output of system (5). Moreover, if $h(x) = 0$ only when $x = 0$, then such a controller would also be stabilizing for (5).

Note that once an estimate of system (8) is available, one can implement \mathcal{L}_1 or \mathcal{L}_2 assuming full-state measurements availability and find a stabilizing controller u_* . However, such a controller cannot be implemented in real scenarios as only ξ_1 is available to measurements in (8). Notice that an estimate of the whole state vector ξ can be retrieved via the high-gain observer (9). It is well-known in the literature that using the estimates of (9) to implement a stabilizing controller requires to consider the saturated controller $\text{sat}_M(u_*(x)) = \max(-M, \min(u_*, M))$ rather than only u_* [7]. It is possible to show that by choosing a suitable M and a sufficiently small ε , the overall controller keeps its stabilization properties.

4 Numerical simulations

In this section, the methods proposed in this paper are validated through numerical simulations¹. Such numerical simulations are carried out in Julia [3] with the aid of the DiffEqFlux.jl package [19]. Such a package provides the implementation of stochastic gradient descent algorithms and techniques to locally compute the partial derivative of loss functions with respect to a set of parameters (see Remark 1).

The first example (Example 1) deals with a simple linear system, whose dynamics are assumed to be completely known and the state is assumed to be fully available to measurements. The aim of this example is to exploit the classical linear analysis tool to show how α in \mathcal{L}_1 relates to robustness and performance. Similarly, Example 2 attempts at showing the same properties for the nonlinear dynamics of a rotating rigid body, whose dynamics are assumed to be only partially known.

Examples 3 and 4 considers two partially known nonlinear systems and the loss function \mathcal{L}_2 in order to show the effectiveness of the numerical feedback linearization approach of Section 2.2 together with the system estimation technique of Section 3.1. Furthermore, the state is assumed to be partially measurable, thus requiring a state observer to complete the controller design (Section 3.2).

Example 1. *Consider the linear system*

$$\dot{x}_1 = x_2, \tag{10a}$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -x_1 + u, \tag{10b}$$

where the state $x = [x_1, x_2]^\top$ is supposed to be fully available for measurements and the system dynamics are fully known. This example aims at showing a simple practical application of the approach of Section 2.1.

By choosing the parametric controller $u(x; p) = p_1 x_1 + p_2 x_2$ and the Lyapunov function candidate $V(x) = x^\top P x$, where

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \tag{11}$$

then one is able to implement the loss function \mathcal{L}_1 . Note that the particular choice of P is motivated by the fact that if one chooses $P = I$, then

$$\dot{V}(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ -x_1 + p_1 x_1 + p_2 x_2 \end{bmatrix} = p_1 x_1 x_2 + p_2 x_2^2,$$

which cannot be negative definite. If one considers (11), then

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{V}(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1 & x_2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ -x_1 + p_1 x_1 + p_2 x_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &= (p_1 + p_2)x_1 x_2 + (p_1 - 1)x_1^2 + p_2 x_2^2, \end{aligned}$$

¹Code available at https://github.com/gsmfnc/UnivEst.jl/tree/main/examples/lyapunov_based_ctrl

which may be negative definite for appropriate choices of p_1 and p_2 .

In order to show the effects of α on the minimization of \mathcal{L}_1 , three minimization problems are considered with $\gamma = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 1, 5$ and 10 . The training set X is generated by taking samples in B_R with $R = 1$. Thus, three possible optimal vectors of parameters are found, i.e. $p_{*,1} = [-2.169, -2.857]^\top$, $p_{*,2} = [-1.027, -1.645]^\top$ and $p_{*,3} = [-0.709, -1.261]^\top$.

Given the linearity of the overall control system, it is possible to draw the bode diagrams of the open-loop transfer function considering the three optimal vectors of parameters. It is shown in Figure 1 that as α decreases, the magnitude of the open-loop transfer function is larger. Noticing that the phase crosses -180 degrees around 1 rad/s, larger magnitudes imply larger gain margins. Moreover, the magnitude crosses 0 dB around 2.5 rad/s, where the phases of all the three transfer functions are comparable. However, for $\alpha = 5$ the magnitude is close to zero also for lower frequencies, whereas for $\alpha = 10$ there is a crossing at 0.3 rad/s. Contextually, for those frequencies, the phase results to be quite close to -180 degrees, thus implying less robustness to phase shifts.

Figure 1: Comparison of the bode diagrams of the open-loop transfer function of system (10) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 1.

Figure 2 depicts the eigenvalues of the closed-loop transfer function for the three stabilizing control laws. It is possible to see that the real part of the eigenvalues is more negative as α is smaller, whereas the imaginary part remains comparable. Therefore, smaller α also implies faster convergence. As a matter of fact, Figure 3 shows that the convergence time of the stabilizing controllers decreases as α decreases. On the other hand, the control effort is larger for

Figure 2: Comparison of the eigenvalues of the closed-loop transfer function of system (10) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 1.

smaller values of α .

By introducing uncertainties in (10), it is also possible to verify that $p_{\star,1}$ yields a more robust controller. For instance, in Figure 4 the response of the system is depicted in the case that (10b) is substituted by $\dot{x}_2 = -x_1 + 0.5u$, whereas in Figure 5 the following dynamics function is considered:

$$\dot{x}_1 = x_2 + (-2.64x_1^2 - 0.561x_2^2 + 0.2651x_1x_2), \quad (12a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = -x_1 + u + (0.7579x_1^2 - 0.3047x_2^2 - 0.4565x_1x_2). \quad (12b)$$

In both figures, it is possible to see that the first controller is able to deal with the added uncertainties better than the other controllers do by showing less oscillations in the former and by not introducing instabilities in the latter.

Example 2. Consider the dynamics of a rotating rigid body [13]:

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{c_1}(c_2 - c_3)x_2x_3 + u_1, \quad (13a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \frac{1}{c_2}(c_3 - c_1)x_3x_1 + u_2, \quad (13b)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = \frac{1}{c_3}(c_1 - c_2)x_1x_2 + u_3, \quad (13c)$$

where $c = [0.5, 0.3, 0.6]^\top$, the state $x = [x_1, x_2, x_3]^\top$ is fully measurable and $x(0) = [0, 0, 0]^\top$. However, suppose that the dynamics function is unknown.

Figure 3: Comparison of the time responses of system (10) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 1.

Assume the availability of measurements of (13) with

$$u(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \sin(2.4944t) \\ \sin(5.9451t) \\ \sin(7.1838t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

for $t \in [0, 50]$ and a sampling time of 0.01s. Thus, using the results of Section 3.1, the dynamics of (13) is estimated via a universal differential equation

$$\dot{\chi} = N(\chi; W) + u, \quad (15)$$

where $u = [u_1, u_2, u_3]^\top$ is defined analogously to (14), N is a two-hidden-layer neural network with 64 hidden nodes and W is the vector of tunable weights. Using \mathcal{L}_3 with $h(\chi) = \chi$, one is able to tune W and, thus, estimate the dynamics function of (13).

System (15) is then used to implement \mathcal{L}_1 with $\gamma = 0.1$, $V(\chi) = \chi^\top \chi$ and $u(\chi) = K(p)\chi$, where

$$K(p) = \begin{bmatrix} p_1 & p_2 & p_3 \\ p_4 & p_5 & p_6 \\ p_7 & p_8 & p_9 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Figure 4: Comparison of the time responses of system (10) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 1 and substituting (10b) with $\dot{x}_2 = -x_1 + 0.5u$.

Figure 5: Comparison of the time responses of system (12) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 1.

Two values for α are considered, i.e. 1 and 10, and the training set X is composed of samples of B_R with $R = 10$. Therefore, two possible optimal vectors of parameters are found:

$$p_{\star,1} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.493 \\ 0.038 \\ -0.036 \\ 0.069 \\ -0.592 \\ 0.164 \\ -0.096 \\ 0.328 \\ -1.256 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad p_{\star,2} = \begin{bmatrix} -0.228 \\ 0.048 \\ -0.047 \\ 0.119 \\ -0.497 \\ 0.236 \\ -0.251 \\ 0.486 \\ -1.067 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Figure 6 shows a comparison between the two responses obtained using $p_{\star,1}$ and $p_{\star,2}$, where a larger convergence rate is observed when considering the former. Furthermore, Figure 7 aims at showing that $p_{\star,1}$ yields a more robust controller compared to $p_{\star,2}$, hence considering the following modified dynamics:

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{c_1}(c_2 - c_3)x_2x_3 + u_1 + k_1\varphi(x), \quad (16a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \frac{1}{c_2}(c_3 - c_1)x_3x_1 + u_2 + k_2\varphi(x), \quad (16b)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = \frac{1}{c_3}(c_1 - c_2)x_1x_2 + u_3 + k_3\varphi(x), \quad (16c)$$

where

$$k_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0.072 \\ 0.111 \\ -0.159 \\ 0.213 \\ -0.252 \\ -0.27 \end{bmatrix}, \quad k_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.384 \\ 0.186 \\ 0.153 \\ -0.135 \\ -0.153 \\ -0.72 \end{bmatrix}, \quad k_3 = \begin{bmatrix} -0.138 \\ 0.738 \\ -0.225 \\ 0.114 \\ -0.078 \\ 0.144 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi(x) = \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \\ x_1^2 \\ x_2^2 \\ x_3^2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The figure confirms that using a smaller α produces a controller with better robustness properties as the controller with $p_{\star,2}$ does not converge to zero when considering the parasitic dynamics introduced in (16).

Example 3. Consider the Duffing oscillator (Equation (2.6) in [23])

$$\dot{x}_1 = x_2, \quad (17a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = \phi(x) + u(t), \quad (17b)$$

$$y = x_1, \quad (17c)$$

where $x(0) = [-0.9, 4]^\top$ and $\phi(x) = -x_2 + x_1 - x_1^3$ are assumed to be unknown. Suppose that the input $u(t) = \sin(0.8t)$ is applied for $t \in [0, 50]$ s and the output is sampled every 0.01s.

Figure 6: Comparison of the time responses of system (13) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 2.

In order to estimate the function $\phi(x)$, the following UDE is considered:

$$\dot{\chi}_1 = \chi_2, \quad (18a)$$

$$\dot{\chi}_2 = N(\chi; W) + u(t), \quad (18b)$$

$$y_\chi = \chi_1, \quad (18c)$$

where N is a two-hidden layer neural network with 64 hidden nodes and W is the vector of tunable weights. Following Section 3.1, such weights are tuned by minimizing \mathcal{L}_3 . Then, system (18) is used to implement \mathcal{L}_2 with $\dot{V}_{des}(x) = x^\top P f_{des}(x)$, $f_{des}(x) = A_{des}x$,

$$A_{des} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -12 & -7 \end{bmatrix}$$

and P being the solution of $A_{des}^\top P + PA_{des} = -I$. Moreover, the input u is

Figure 7: Comparison of the time responses of system (16) with the stabilizing control laws obtained by varying α as explained in Example 2.

parameterized as

$$u(x; p) = p^\top \begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_1^2 \\ x_2^2 \\ x_1 x_2 \\ x_1^3 \\ x_2^3 \\ x_1^2 x_2 \\ x_1 x_2^2 \end{bmatrix},$$

where $p \in \mathbb{R}^9$ are tunable parameters. By minimizing \mathcal{L}_2 on the training set X composed of samples in B_R , with $R = 5$, one finds

$$p_\star = [-11.21 \quad -6.09 \quad 0.10 \quad 0.04 \quad 0.01 \quad 0.02 \quad 0 \quad 0.01 \quad 0.01]^\top.$$

Given the unavailability of x_2 to measurements, the optimal controller is implemented using the estimate of x obtained via the high-gain observer (9) with $\varepsilon = 10^{-4}$, $k_1 = 0.3$, $k_2 = 0.02$ and the function g being substituted by

$N(\chi; W) + u_*$. Note that the high-gain observer provides estimates of x as the Duffing oscillator is already in observability canonical form. Moreover, the control input u_* is saturated with $M = 40$. Numerical simulations are shown in Figure 8, where the response of the overall control system is compared with the response of the desired dynamics $\dot{x} = f_{des}(x)$. One can notice that the time response of the desired dynamics is reproduced by the control system from several initial conditions: most of the times when the two responses “far” correspond to the times when x is outside the set B_R , where the controller is computed.

Figure 8: Comparison of the time responses of system (17) with $u = \text{sat}_M(u(x; p_*))$ and the desired dynamics $\dot{x} = f_{des}(x)$ as defined in Example 3, starting from several initial conditions.

Example 4. Consider the Chua's circuit CV_1 (Table 3.4 in [23])

$$\dot{x}_1 = p_1x_2 + p_2x_1 + p_3x_1^3, \quad (19a)$$

$$\dot{x}_2 = p_4x_1 + p_5x_3, \quad (19b)$$

$$\dot{x}_3 = p_6x_2 + u, \quad (19c)$$

$$y = x_1, \quad (19d)$$

where $p = [0.3, 1.0, -1.0, 1.0, 1.0, -1.0]^\top$ is a vector of unknown parameters and $x(0) = [0, -3, 1]^\top$. System (19) can be rewritten in the following observability canonical form by considering the third-order observability map:

$$\dot{\chi}_1 = \chi_2, \quad (20a)$$

$$\dot{\chi}_2 = \chi_3, \quad (20b)$$

$$\dot{\chi}_3 = -p_3p_5p_6 + p_5p_6\chi_1^3\chi_2 + p_1p_4\chi_2 - p_2p_5p_6\chi_1 + 3p_3\chi_1^2\chi_3 \quad (20c)$$

$$+ p_2\chi_3 + 6p_3\chi_1\chi_2^2 + p_1p_5u,$$

$$y = \chi_1. \quad (20d)$$

Assume $u(t) = \sin(t)$ for $t \in [0, 20]s$. By defining an UDE analogous to (20), one can estimate the parameters vector p minimizing \mathcal{L}_3 , as explained in Section 3.1. Such an UDE can then be used to implement \mathcal{L}_2 with $\dot{V}_{des}(\chi) = \chi^\top P f_{des}(\chi)$, $f_{des}(\chi) = A_{des}\chi$,

$$A_{des} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ -2 & -2 & -2 \end{bmatrix},$$

P being the solution of $A_{des}^\top P + PA_{des} = -I$ and the training set X composed of samples of B_R with $R = 2.5$. Moreover, the input u is parameterized as $u(\chi; p) = p^\top \phi(\chi)$, where $\phi(\chi)$ are all the monomials of the variable $\chi = (\chi_1, \chi_2, \chi_3)$ from order one to order three.

Given the unavailability of χ_2 and χ_3 to measurements, an high-gain observer is designed following Section 3.2 with $\varepsilon = 10^{-3}$, $k_1 = 0.6$, $k_2 = 0.11$ and $k_3 = 0.006$. Moreover, the function g is substituted by the right-hand side of (20c) with $u = \text{sat}_M(u(\hat{\chi}, p_\star))$ and $M = 5$. Then, using the estimation of χ provided by such an observer, numerical simulations of the overall control system are shown in Figure 9. Note that only x_1 and $\chi_{1,des}$ are comparable as the other entries of the state vector are solutions to different differential equations.

5 Conclusions

Two different approaches are proposed in this paper to design feedback controllers. Unknown dynamics and non-availability of full-state measurements are dealt with by coupling system identification and nonlinear observer design techniques taken from the literature. Then, several numerical simulations are

Figure 9: Time responses of system (19) with $u = u(\hat{x}; p_*)$ as defined in Example 4 from several initial conditions.

given in order to verify the overall design procedure and the theoretical claims. Further developments will attempt to include possible disturbances into the optimization problem in order to find robust control laws with respect to different sources of error. Moreover, possible applications to trajectory planning will be considered.

References

- [1] F. Berkenkamp, R. Moriconi, A. P. Schoellig, and A. Krause. Safe learning of regions of attraction for uncertain, nonlinear systems with gaussian processes. In *2016 IEEE 55th Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*, pages 4661–4666. IEEE, 2016.
- [2] F. Berkenkamp, M. Turchetta, A. Schoellig, and A. Krause. Safe model-based reinforcement learning with stability guarantees. *Advances in neural*

- information processing systems*, 30, 2017.
- [3] J. Bezanson, A. Edelman, S. Karpinski, and V. B. Shah. Julia: A fresh approach to numerical computing. *SIAM review*, 59(1):65–98, 2017.
 - [4] J. C. Butcher. A history of runge-kutta methods. *Applied numerical mathematics*, 20(3):247–260, 1996.
 - [5] Y.-C. Chang, N. Roohi, and S. Gao. Neural lyapunov control. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 32, 2019.
 - [6] Y. Chow, O. Nachum, E. Duenez-Guzman, and M. Ghavamzadeh. A lyapunov-based approach to safe reinforcement learning. *Advances in neural information processing systems*, 31, 2018.
 - [7] F. Esfandiari and H. K. Khalil. Output feedback stabilization of fully linearizable systems. *International Journal of control*, 56(5):1007–1037, 1992.
 - [8] J. P. Gauthier and I. Kupka. *Deterministic observation theory and applications*. Cambridge university press, 2001.
 - [9] F. Gismondi. *Data-driven and adaptive approaches for system identification, observer design and controller synthesis*. PhD thesis, University of Rome Tor Vergata, 2024.
 - [10] F. Gismondi, C. Possieri, and A. Tornambe. Design of neural high-gain observers for autonomous nonlinear systems using universal differential equations. *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, pages 1–13, 2022.
 - [11] A. Isidori. *Nonlinear control systems: an introduction*. Springer, 1985.
 - [12] A. J. Jerri. The shannon sampling theorem—its various extensions and applications: A tutorial review. *Proc. of the IEEE*, 65(11):1565–1596, 1977.
 - [13] H. K. Khalil. *Nonlinear systems*. Prentice Hall, 3rd edition, 2002.
 - [14] H. K. Khalil. *High-gain observers in nonlinear feedback control*. Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2017.
 - [15] D. P. Kingma and J. Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization. arXiv:1412.6980, 2014.
 - [16] M. Krstić, I. Kanellakopoulos, and P. V. Kokotović. *Nonlinear and adaptive control design*. Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1995.
 - [17] J. Nocedal and S. Wright. *Numerical optimization*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2006.
 - [18] D. P. Petersen and D. Middleton. Sampling and reconstruction of wave-number-limited functions in n-dimensional euclidean spaces. *Information and control*, 5(4):279–323, 1962.

- [19] C. Rackauckas, Y. Ma, J. Martensen, C. Warner, K. Zubov, R. Supekar, D. Skinner, A. Ramadhan, and A. Edelman. Universal differential equations for scientific machine learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.04385*, 2020.
- [20] S. M. Richards, F. Berkenkamp, and A. Krause. The lyapunov neural network: Adaptive stability certification for safe learning of dynamical systems. In *Conference on robot learning*, pages 466–476. PMLR, 2018.
- [21] C. E. Shannon. Communication in the presence of noise. *Proc. of the IRE Transactions on Information Theory*, 37(1):10–21, 1949.
- [22] J. J. E. Slotine and W. Li. Applied nonlinear control. *Prentice Hall*, 1991.
- [23] J. C. Sprott. *Elegant chaos: algebraically simple chaotic flows*. World Scientific, 2010.
- [24] R. S. Sutton and A. G. Barto. *Reinforcement learning: An introduction*. MIT press, 2018.
- [25] A. Tornambè. High-gain observers for non-linear systems. *International Journal of Systems Science*, 23(9):1475–1489, 1992.
- [26] V. I. Utkin. *Sliding modes in control and optimization*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2013.
- [27] L. Yang, H. Dai, Z. Shi, C.-J. Hsieh, R. Tedrake, and H. Zhang. Lyapunov-stable neural control for state and output feedback: A novel formulation. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2404.07956*, 2024.